

The juxtaglomerular apparatus and the pressure model of kidney function

Johan Nygren

johanngrn@gmail.com

In the kidney, flow resistance peaks at two points in the filtration system, at the thin segment in the loop of Henle, and, in the collecting duct tree as it approaches the papilla (Knepper, 2018). These high resistance regions might be a physiological adaptation that has been evolutionarily selected for. The increase in hydrostatic pressure within the tubules has an effect analogous to the hydrostatic pressure component in capillary exchange, and favours reabsorption of whatever the tubule epithelia is most permeable to. If the tubule epithelium is most permeable to water, these high pressure regions would have evolved to concentrate the filtrate.

The model described in the previous paragraph implies that the physiological function of the loop of Henle requires a pressurized filtrate. The flow rate of filtrate at the thin segment in the loop of Henle relies on the filtration rate at the glomeruli, the glomerular filtration rate. When glomerular filtration rate falls, the ability of the thin segment in the loop of Henle to concentrate the filtrate falls. This impacts the countercurrent multiplication (CCM) in the thick ascending limb (TAL), a lower salt concentration in the filtrate in the TAL prevents CCM from using the normally high gradient (that the thin segment produces.) The dilute filtrate also means the macula densa cells in the distal tubule will receive dilute filtrate, and, activate their reflex pathway to a fall in filtrate sodium chloride. This reflex pathway has a primary purpose of increasing glomerular filtration rate, which fixes the problem the JGA is primarily meant to monitor: a loss of pressure at the thin segment in the loop of Henle. The macula densa cells also respond to loss of pressure in the filtrate, for the same reasons.

The later steps in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) is secondary in importance to maintaining loop of Henle functionality: countercurrent multiplication, but it is still important. The loss of pressure at the thin segment implies or equates a loss of pressure at the second high resistance region in the renal pyramids, the root of the collecting duct tree. This low pressure can be resolved by contraction of the renal medulla (Martinez, 2019). In the same way vasopressin contracts vascular smooth muscle, it can also act on contractile fibroblasts within the renal interstitium (Martinez, 2019). Jakob Henle pointed to the smooth muscle like appearance of the renal medulla in his original *Zur Anatomie der Niere* from 1862 where he also described the tubular loops that are now named after him,

"I thought it was a kind of interstitial connective tissue, but emphasized its resemblance to the elements of organic muscle tissue. Virchow declared them to be muscle fiber cells; Frerichs left their origins uncertain"

Vasopressin released via the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system will contract the medulla, and this will maintain pressure at the second high resistance region in the kidney, the collecting duct tip. This pressure, like hydrostatic pressure in capillary exchange, has the ability to drive reabsorption of that which the collecting duct epithelia is most permeable to, and if this was water, it would be an ideal mechanism to concentrate urine, and it would explain the RAAS system and the priorities the kidney makes around its own function as well as endocrine control of the entire body.

References

- Rodríguez-Martínez, M., López-Rodríguez, J. F., Flores-Sandoval, O., Calvo-Turrubiarres, M. Z., Sánchez-Briones, M. E., Silva-Ramírez, A. S., & Guerreiro-Ojeda, V. (2019). Additional evidence that the rat renal interstitium contracts in vivo. *PLOS ONE*, 14(11), e0225640. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0225640>
- Gilmer, G. G., Deshpande, V. G., Chou, C.-L., & Knepper, M. (2018). Flow resistance along the rat renal tubule. *American Journal of Physiology-Renal Physiology*, 315(5), F1398–F1405. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajprenal.00219.2018>